

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF OPTICAL FIBERS EMBEDDED SMART GEOCOMPOSITE

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1. Introduction

Various types of geosynthetics can be used in civil and environmental engineering structures, and in particular, geonet and geotextile-related composites are widely used for drainage purposes in various conditions.

The fiber-reinforced materials for disaster protection are generally classified as geotextile, geonet / geogrid, geomembrane and geocomposite. Among them, geocomposite is defined as fiber-reinforced complex which has two or more functions. The basic strategy in producing the geocomposite is how to obtain the best features of different materials in such a way that specific applications are addressed in the optimal manner and at minimum cost. Geocomposites which has the properties of high constructability, economics, and environmental friendliness, are extensively used in wide civil engineering structures, ground separation, retaining wall separation / reinforcement / drainage, landfill protection and shore protection system [1-3]. By the reason of geotechnical structures, the demand of geocomposite, especially drainage geocomposite, has been increased. Geocomposites for drainage are generally composed of geotextile layer(often non-woven)bonded either side of a discharge capacity core. Therefore 20mm thick geocomposites can have the same flow capacity as a 300mm thick granular layer.

Recently, geocomposites have been actively developed to provide high performances and multi-function. At this time, the necessity for developing multi-axial geocomposite is increased due to enhances the workability and the actual advancement in the field of soil structural reinforcement function.

Also, the interests in structural monitoring of civil infrastructures are increased. Especially, as the civil infrastructures such as bridges, tunnels, train rails and buildings become large scale, it is necessary to monitor and maintain the safety state of the structures which requires smart systems that can supply long-term monitoring during the service time of the structures [4].

In this study, multi-layer geocomposite which nonwoven geotextile is combined with multi-axial wrap knitted fabric were prepared. The optical fiber cable was embedded in it in order to monitor and inspect its deformation during use after installation. Multi-layered smart geocomposites were characterized in the aspects of multi-axial reinforcement, multiple functions and real-time inspection.

2. Experimental

2.1 Fiber spinning process

The polypropylene(PP) staple fibers for geotextile were prepared through melt spinning line(KITECH,

Korea)(Figure 1). The basic PP resins(HP552R, Polymirae Co., Korea) were mixed with master batch PP chips(UV-9700, SAM-A C&I Co., Korea) which contain the ultraviolet(UV) stabilizer. This UV stabilizer can prevent the fiber from the photo degradation when it is exposed to UV radiation. The molten PP resin was extruded in into nozzle, drawn and then crimped. The crimped fiber bundle was cut into 51 mm length, becoming the staple fibers. The staple fibers with 3 denier × 51 mm length were produced. The process conditions of staple fiber spinning are shown in Table.1.

2.2 Non-woven geotextile process

Several nonwovens were prepared at various conditions from the staple fibers through carding, cross lapping and needle punching processes. Figure 2 shows the pilot scale nonwoven production line(KITECH, Korea). The basic weights of needle punched nonwovens were 200, 250, and 300 g/m². The conditions of nonwoven process are shown in Table 2. The needle punched nonwoven was laminated with meltblown PP web which consists of fine fibers. The meltblown fine PP fibers were laid down on the needle punched nonwoven during melt blowing spinning. The spinning temperature of melt blowing and weight of meltblown web were 240°C and 20 g/m², respectively.

2.3 Preparation of multi-axial geocomposite

Multi-axial warp knitted fabric was prepared in various types such as woven, grid, nonwoven and so on. These multi-axially stitched fabrics were bonded with geotextile by stitching process. Table 3 shows the production conditions. During this procedure, optical fiber cable was embedded between geotextile and multi-axial wrap knitted fabric using a certain stitching wheel pattern technology which can minimize the damage of optical fiber(Figure 3, 4).

2.4 Characterizations

The samples prepared through several producing steps were characterized with various analyses such as tensile, pore size, chemical resistance, creep, weather ability and so on. The geocomposite embedded with optical fiber cable were characterized in terms of optical attenuation.

3. Results and Conclusion

3.1 Pore size of non-woven geotextile

Table 4 shows the mean flow and bubble point pore diameters of non-woven geotextiles prepared. The mean and maximum pore diameters became smaller as an increase of the basis weight of PP+UV geotextile. Also, they became smaller more after lamination of PP meltblown web with needle punched PP+UV nonwoven, indicating that introduction of fine fiber web can be effective to enhance the separation property.

3.2 Tensile strength of non-woven geotextile

Tensile strengths of the three kinds of non-woven geotextiles were summarized in Table 5. Max force was generally proportional to an increase of the basis weight of PP+UV nonwoven but elongation at max was inverse proportional.

3.3. Chemical resistance test of geocomposite

To investigate the chemical resistance, the geocomposite was immersed in acid (0.025M H₂SO₄) or base (Ca(OH)₂ 2.5g in 1L water) at 60 °C for 3 days, and then completely dried after water washing. Table 6 shows tensile strength and strength retention of geocomposite before and after treatment. The geocomposite after chemical

treatment showed the strength retention above 90% and no change in elongation when compared with that of pristine sample, presenting that the geocomposite prepared has a good chemically stable.

3.5. Accelerated creep test of geocomposite

Tensile strength of geocomposite was evaluated at the strain rate of (20 ± 5) %/min according to the KS K ISO 10319. Average tensile strength and elongation were 164.8 KN/m and 10.6%, respectively (Table 7).

In order to assess the long-term creep properties of geocomposite prepared, the accelerated creep test was performed according to ASTM D 6992. The creep loads were 40, 50, 60% of ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and the total test duration is 72,000 sec. The conditions of the test were shown in Table 8 in detail. The creep master curve was obtained from the results of the accelerated creep test at the creep load 40, 50, 60% of UTS. The creep strain after 50 and 100 years of life time which was calculated from creep master curves was shown in Table 8. The creep strain after 50 and 100 years of life time was 11.2% and 11.4%, respectively when 40% of UTS was applied (Table 9). These indicate that geocomposite prepared has the long-term stability with a low dimensional change.

3.6 Water permeability of geocomposite

Water permeability was tested according to ISO 11058. It is determined by measuring the water quantity that passes through a test specimen in a specific time interval under a specific normal stress and a specific hydraulic gradient. The water permeability coefficient of geotextile was 3.5×10^{-3} cm/s and that of geocomposite which geotextile and multi-axial warp knitted fabric are combined by stitching was 2.1×10^{-3} cm/s (Table 10). This could be

considered as appropriate value when it is used in field

3.7 Apparent opening size of geotextile and geocomposite

Apparent Opening Size (AOS) was tested according to ASTM D 4751. This test method is used to indicate the AOS in a geotextile that reflects the approximate largest opening dimension available for soil to pass through. Apparent opening size of geotextile was 38 microns. That of geocomposite was 105 microns which is larger than that of geotextile (Figure 5). This could be caused by pore enlargement during stitching process to combine the geotextile with multi-axial warp knitted fabric.

3.8 Accelerated weathering test of geocomposite

Accelerated weathering test was performed with 120 min cycle method. Specimens were experienced 150 cycles (total 300 hrs) which one cycle is light irradiation for 102 minutes and water spray for 18 minutes. The lamp used in this test is xenon arc type.

The tensile strength of geocomposite after weathering test for 300hrs was decreased from 3,212 to 2,954 N, indicating the 91% tensile strength retention (Table 11)

3.9 Clogging property of geocomposite

The schematic diagram of test equipment for clogging performance is shown in Figure 6. This tester is composed of manometer, constant head device and cylindrical, transparent plastic permeameter in which soil (average diameter: 500 to 600 microns) is filled on the top of geocomposite specimen. Measurements of differential heads and flow rates are taken at different time intervals to determine hydraulic gradients.

Figure 7 shows the gradient ratio (GR) as a function of time at different hydraulic gradients. The GR value of geocomposite was less than 3,

representing that the soil clogging on geocomposite occur less frequently, therefore less affect on the reduction of drainage performance.

3.10 Optical attenuation of geocomposite

The optical fiber embedded smart geocomposites are shown in Figure 8. Optical fiber cable was embedded in different geometric matrix such as grid, fabric and warp knitting structures. The optical fiber cable was effectively embedded in the matrix with no disconnection as a result of laser transmission (Figure 9). The optical attenuation was very low within 0.3 dB, indicating geocomposite can be effectively applied in real-time monitoring on deformation of geocomposite after installation.

Figure 1. Melt spinning equipment for staple fiber

Table 1. Process conditions of staple fiber spinning

Staple fiber spinning condition		
Extruder Temp.	°C	220
Spinneret Temp.	°C	240
Cooling Temp.	°C	10
Cooling RPM	RPM	75
Draw ratio	-	3:1
Godet roll temp.	°C	65~70
Cutting Length	mm	51
Target Denier	Den	3

Figure 2. Pilot scale nonwoven production line

Table 2. The conditions of nonwoven process

Process conditions		
Carding	Doffer	24.5
	(m/min)	
Cross lapping	Traverse width	840
	(mm)	
	Web feeder	3.0
	(m/min)	
Needle punching	Needle stroke	1step: 600
		2step: 100
	Needle depth	1step: -4
		2step: 55

Figure 3. Special stitching pattern wheel

Table 3. The process conditions for geocomposite

	Process condition	
	DBLT850	LT635/PM25
Gauge	6	10
I Gear	30.75	33.03
Angle	0/90/+45	0/90
Reed	12/8/12/8	12/7/12
Stitch Gear	67/43	36/40
O° Gear	60/54	37/51
Vorsate	40.00	33.93
Stitch	11/12/11/12	10/11 - 11/12/11/12
	23/12/23/21	12/11 - 23/12/23/21
	11/22/11/22	11/10 - 11/22/11/22
Thread	20/26/20	16/10/16

Figure 4. Geocomposite embedded with optical fiber

Table 4. Pore size of non-woven geotextiles

Sample	Mean flow pore diameter (Microns)	Bubble point pore diameter (Microns)
PP+UV(200 g/m ²)	44.8	106.2
PP+UV(250 g/m ²)	32.3	94.9
PP+UV(250 g/m ²) +PP(MB 20 g/m ²)	13.8	22.9

Table 5. Tensile strength of non-woven geotextile

Sample		Max Force (N)	Elong at Max (%)
PP+UV (200 g/m ²)	MD	255	177
	CD	500	140
PP+UV (250 g/m ²)	MD	322	171
	CD	646	121
PP+UV (300 g/m ²)	MD	490	144
	CD	981	98

Table 6. Tensile strength and strength retention of geocomposite after chemical resistance test

Geocomposite	Tensile strength (KN/m)	Elongation (%)	Strength retention (%)
Pristine	80	15	-
Acid treatment	72	15	90
Base treatment	75	14	94

Table 7. Tensile strength of geocomposite

Geocomposite		
Division	Tensile strength (KN/m)	Elongation (%)
1	166.7	11.2
2	167.6	10.2
3	160.0	10.5
Average	164.8	10.6

Table 8. The conditions of accelerated creep test

Reference Temperature (°C)	Heating Temperature (°C)	Final Temperature (°C)	Isothermal maintain Time (s)
20	14	90	12,000

Table 9. Accelerated creep strain of geocomposite in the life time

Life time (Year)	Creep strain (%)		
	Creep load 40 %	Creep load 50%	Creep load 60%
50	7.1	11.2	13.2
100	7.1	11.4	13.4

Table 10. Water permeability of geotextile and geocomposite

Sample	Water permeability (m/s)
Geotextile	3.5×10^{-3}
Geocomposite	2.1×10^{-3}

Figure 5. Determining apparent opening size of geotextile and geocomposite

Figure 7. Clogging test result according to gradient ratio

Table 11. Tensile strength of geocomposite before and after weathering test

Weathering test	Tensile strength (N)	Strength retention (%)
Before	3,212	-
After	2,954	91

Figure 8. Optical fibers embedded geogrid, fabric and multi-axial warp knitted geocomposites

Figure 6. Clogging performance test equipment

Figure 9. Optical attenuation evaluation of optical fibers embedded geocomposite

Reference

- [1] St. Paul, A Design Primer: Geotextiles and Related Materials-First Edition, Industrial Fabric Association International Geotextile Division, USA 1992
- [2] A. W. Sintef and S. H. Chew, "Geosynthetic Damage - From Laboratory to Field", Geosynthetics - 7th ICG 2002 : 1203-1226
- [3] M.M. Schwartz, "Composite Materials Handbook", 2th ed., McGraw-Hill, New York, 1992.
- [4] Kim, Ki-Soo "Fiber Optic Sensor For Smart Monitoring, Earthquake Engineering Society of Korea Vol.52, 2006